

LOW-COST SYNTHESIS OF p-CuAlO₂ NANOPARTICLES AND STUDY OF SIZE-DEPENDENT OPTICAL PROPERTIES FOR TRANSPARENT NANOELECTRONIC APPLICATIONS

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1 Introduction

Delafossite transparent conducting oxides (TCO) with crystallographic structure ABO₂ (where A represents monovalent cations like Cu, Ag and B represents trivalent cations such as Al, In, Cr, Co, Sc, Ga etc.), have attracted renewed interest in thin film technology after the report of p-type conductivity in the transparent film of CuAlO₂ [1,2], which has opened up a new field in optoelectronic device technology, the so-called 'transparent' or 'invisible' electronics [3], where a combination of the two types of TCOs (n-type and p-type semiconducting) in the form of an active (p-n) junction could lead to a 'functional' window, which would transmit the visible portion of solar radiation but could generate electricity by the absorption of the ultra violet (UV) part. Therefore, this kind of transparent junctions can be used as an UV absorber for the application of UV-based solar cells, thus extending the absorption spectrum of the incident radiation of current solar cell applications into the higher energy range to improve the cell efficiency. Also recent advancements in the field of nanotechnology offer tremendous opportunities in optoelectronics industry because of the drastic difference of the optical properties of the nanocrystals against the respective bulk materials, which are markedly related to the nanosize and surface chemistry of the nanomaterials and explained in terms of quantum confinement effect [4]. In that respect, syntheses and characterizations of nanocrystalline p-TCOs as a counterpart of existing nanostructured n-TCOs (like ZnO, InSnO₃, SnO₂:F/Sb, Cd₂SnO₄ etc.) can be a very important area of research for all-transparent nanoactive devices, which may give a new dimension in the field of transparent electronics. Various research groups around the globe have reported the syntheses of several p-type transparent conducting oxide thin films via physical and

chemical fabrication techniques and also reported on the device fabrications using these p-TCOs [5-10].

As far as synthesis of nanocrystalline CuAlO₂ is concerned, Gong and co-authors [11] prepared phase impure nanostructured copper aluminum oxide films by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method, whereas Gao and co-authors [12] reported the synthesis of phase pure nanocrystalline CuAlO₂ thin film by spin-on technique. We have previously reported the synthesis of CuAlO₂ nanoparticles by both physical and wet-chemical techniques [13-14]. Although physical techniques are sometimes costlier than wet-chemical techniques due to the requirement of expensive vacuum systems and accessories, but always preferred due to its compatibility with solid state IC CMOS fabrication processes for possible device applications [15]. Amongst various physical deposition processes, sputtering technique is considered to be highly effective both in research-scale as well as in industrial-scale due to its cost-effectivity, simplicity and ability for large area deposition, which can lead to volume production with easy coating on a wide range of substrates with complex geometries [16].

2 Experimental

Firstly, polycrystalline CuAlO₂ powder is synthesized by sintering method using stoichiometric mixture of Cu₂O and Al₂O₃ at 1100°C, which is subsequently pelletized to sputter target for nanoparticle deposition inside a vertical dc sputter system evacuated to a base pressure of 10⁻⁶ mbar. Films are deposited on ultrasonically cleaned glass and Si substrates under oxygen-diluted Ar atmosphere (2:3 volume ratio) with an electrode distance around 2.0 cm. Substrate temperature is kept at a relatively lower value of 373 K to reduce the particle agglomeration

during deposition to maintain the nanostructure of the deposited particles, whereas the deposition time is varied from 5 min to 15 min to observe the size-effect on the optical properties of the nanoparticles. The deposition process is similar to that adopted in [14]. Structural and microstructural characterizations are done by x-ray powder diffraction (XRD) and scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) whereas optical properties are determined via UV-Vis spectrophotometer and photoluminescence apparatus.

3 Results and discussion

Fig. 1(a) shows the XRD pattern of the as-synthesized CuAlO₂ powder, which was used for target preparation. Fig. 1(b) shows the same for CuAlO₂ nanoparticles deposited for 15 min. The patterns closely reflect the rhombohedral crystal structure with $R\bar{3}m$ space group [17], confirming the proper phase formation of delafossite CuAlO₂. Also, due to the nanocrystalline nature, the XRD peaks of nanoparticles are found to be broader and intensities are quite lower than that of target powder. Nanoparticles deposited for 5 and 10 min, the proper phase formation is confirmed through selected area electron diffraction (SAED) of STEM analyses as the signal-to-noise ratio of XRD data are very low in these cases due to lesser particle sizes, as discussed below. High-resolution (HR)-TEM images of CuAlO₂ nanoparticles (cf. Fig. 2a, b, c) for deposition times 5, 10 and 15 min show the average particle sizes around 15, 20 and 25 nm respectively. Obviously, greater deposition times lead to higher particle sizes due to agglomeration of the sputtered particles as often found in sputtering process. Insets of Fig. 2 show the corresponding First Fourier Transform (FFT) micrographs, which correspond to the characteristics crystal planes of the CuAlO₂, confirming the proper phase formation of the nanoparticles.

Optical transmission spectra (T) as a function of the wavelengths (λ) of the incident photons of CuAlO₂ nanoparticles deposited for 5, 10 and 15 min are shown in Fig. 3. Nanoparticles are deposited on glass substrates with a bare glass as reference. Therefore the representative spectra are purely for the samples under test. The average visible transmittance of these films increases from 75% to 95% with decrease in the deposition time. Nanoparticles with least size (15 nm) show maximum transmittance, which is basically due to lesser absorption and scattering of photons on smaller nanoparticles. From the transmittance data, absorption (α) and extinction (k) coefficients are measured at the spectral region of absorption edge using Manifacier model [18] as

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{d} \ln \left(\frac{1}{T} \right) \quad (1)$$

and

$$k = \frac{\lambda \alpha}{4\pi} \quad (2)$$

where d is the film thickness (equated with the average nanoparticle sizes, assuming spherical particles). Spectral variations of α and k is shown at the insets of Fig. 3, which shows significant variations in the values as a function of the nanoparticle sizes, and also comparable to the predicted ranges reported earlier [9, 19-20]. In the range of the onset of the absorption edges, which correspond to the electron excitation from the valence band to the conduction band, the nature and the values of the optical bandgaps (E_g) can be determined by the relation for parabolic bands [21] as

$$(ah\nu)^{1/n} = A(h\nu - E_g) \quad (3)$$

where A is a constant and n is an exponent, both of which depend on the type of transition taking place within the material. Generally, $n = 1/2$ gives direct-allowed transition, $n = 2$ represents indirect-allowed transition and $n = 3/2$ gives direct-forbidden transition. Fig. 4 shows the $(ah\nu)^2$ vs. $h\nu$ plots for nanoparticles with three different sizes to determine the direct bandgaps of the nanoparticles. Extrapolating the linear portion of the plots to the $h\nu$ -axis, the direct bandgap values of the nanomaterials are obtained as 3.70, 3.81 and 3.93 eV for nanoparticle sizes of 25 nm, 20 nm and 15 nm, respectively. The variation of the bandgap and particle size with deposition time is shown in Table 1. From the table we have observed the broadening of the bandgap of the CuAlO₂ nanoparticles with decrease in the particle size. This may be attributed to the quantum confinement effect of size dependency of the bandgap often found in semiconductor nanocrystals [4] and described as

$$\Delta E = \frac{h^2}{8\mu^* r^2} - \frac{1.8e^2}{\epsilon r} \quad (4)$$

where ΔE is the bandgap enhancement ($= E_{nano} - E_{bulk}$), μ^* is the reduced mass of electron-hole effective masses, r is the radius of the nanoparticles (assumed to be spherical and can be equated to $1/L$, where L is the nanoparticle diameters in our case), ϵ is the dielectric constant of the material under test, h and e are Plank's constant and electronic charge, respectively. First term in the right-hand-side of Eq. 4 is the particle-in-a-box quantum localization energy as it has a $1/r^2$ dependency, second term is Coulomb energy with $1/r$ dependency.

Here we neglect the Rydberg energy term, which corresponds to the spatial correlation as the magnitude of this term is considerably lower than the other two terms for widegap materials [4]. Using $\mu^* = 0.03m_0$ (m_0 = free electron mass), $\epsilon = 3.5$ and $E_{bulk} = 3.6$ eV, reported earlier

[14], calculated values of ΔE (ΔE_{calc}) is compared with that obtained from experimental data (ΔE_{expt}) in Fig. 5 and found to fall closely within 10% of the experimental values. Thus the blue-shift of the bandgap with decrease in the size of the CuAlO₂ nanoparticles can be considered to be due to the quantum size effect, as often found in semiconductor nanocrystals.

4 Conclusions

In conclusion, CuAlO₂ nanoparticles are deposited via a cost-effective dc sputtering technique. Nanoparticle sizes are varied from 15 nm to 25 nm by changing the deposition time. XRD and STEM analyses confirm the proper phase formation of the material. HRTEM data confirms the nanocrystalline structure of the as-deposited nanoparticles. Optical transmission spectra showed almost 75% to 95% transmittance of the nanomaterials. Bandgap calculations show that the material has direct bandgap which varied from 3.70 eV to 3.93 eV for a decrease in the particle size which is consistent with size quantization of nanocrystals. The p-type conductivity of the nanoparticles is confirmed via hot-probe method. Therefore, the cost-effective fabrication of this important p-type semiconducting transparent nanomaterial can become very useful for transparent nanoelectronics application in nano-active devices.

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Table 1 Variation of average particle size (L) and bandgap (E_g) with the deposition time.

Deposition time (min)	L (nm)	E _g (eV)
5	15	3.93
10	20	3.81
15	25	3.70

Fig. 1 XRD pattern of (a) CuAlO₂ powder pellet, (b) CuAlO₂ nanoparticles deposited for 15 min.

Fig. 3 Optical transmission spectra of CuAlO₂ nanoparticles deposited for 5 min (---), 10 min (---) and 15 min (---). Inset shows the corresponding spectral variation of extinction coefficients (*k*) and absorption coefficients (*α*) at different deposition times.

Fig. 2 HRTEM micrographs of CuAlO₂ nanoparticles deposited for (a) 5 min, (b) 10 min and (c) 15 min. Insets show the FFT images, which correspond to the characteristic crystal planes of CuAlO₂.

Fig. 4 Determination of direct bandgap values of CuAlO₂ nanoparticles with three different sizes.

Fig. 5 Comparison between the experimentally obtained bandgap enhancements with that theoretically calculated from Eq. 4.